

A distinction between 1,5- and 1,8-dimethoxy anthraquinones using IR of the demethylated product

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Abstract : When spectral data for a naturally occurring compound suggests two alternative structures involving 1,5- and 1,8-dimethoxy anthraquinones; IR of the demethylated compound helps in choosing the correct structure.

Keywords : Dimethoxy anthraquinones, IR, demethylation.

Introduction

It has been shown earlier¹ that ¹H NMR O-alkylation and O-glycosylation shifts are useful for structural studies in naturally occurring anthraquinones. It has been observed further that there are several reports suggesting two alternative structures for anthraquinones. Spectral data in such cases failed to make a distinction between two isomeric structures. It does not draw a line of distinction between 1,5- and 1,8-dimethoxy anthraquinones and their related compounds. It has been shown here that IR of the demethylated compound is helpful in characterising such naturally occurring anthraquinones.

An isolate² from stony coral *Tubastraea micrantha* has been proposed to be 1,8-dimethoxy-7-hydroxy-2,3-methylenedioxy anthraquinone (1) or 1,5-dimethoxy-6-hydroxy-2,3-methylenedioxy anthraquinone (2). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) data for the aromatic protons has been shown along with structures.

A compound isolated³ from suspension cultures of *Cinchona ledgeriana* has been assigned the structure 1,2,5,6-tetramethoxyanthraquinone (3). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃-CD₃OD) for the same has been shown along with structure (3). It has been observed⁴ that it is difficult to rule out the isomeric structure (4).

Three pigments⁵ isolated from callus culture of *Cinchona ledgeriana* have been proposed to have structure 5 (or 6); 7 (or 8) and 9 (or 10). The alternative structure 6 has been proposed⁶ at a later stage.

If 1 (or 2), 3 (or 4), 5 (or 6), 7 (or 8) are demethylated (OMe to OH), then IR of the corresponding product will

help in ascertaining the identity of the natural product. Two carbonyl peaks⁷ are obtained for 1,8-dihydroxy anthraquinones (1678, 1621 cm^{-1}). Only one carbonyl peak⁷ is obtained in 1,5-dihydroxy anthraquinones (1634 cm^{-1}). When chrysophanol dimethyl ether (**11**) was demethylated, chrysophanol (**12**) had been obtained⁸ and it showed two carbonyl peaks in the IR (1670, 1620 cm^{-1}).

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Demethylation of **9** (or **10**) will not enable IR to make a distinction between 1,5- or 1,8-dihydroxy anthraquinones and the reason behind the same is the presence of 4-OH in the demethylated product. A single carbonyl peak is expected for 1,2,3,4,5- or 1,2,3,4,8-pentahydroxy anthraquinones (demethylated products). The example has been incorporated here to pinpoint that IR may fail in making the required distinction.

It has already been observed⁹ that two peaks for C=O are obtained in CMR even when both the carbonyls are chelated as evident from the spectrum of **13** (δ 187.9 and 186.8). When one C=O is chelated and another is non-chelated, expected two peaks for C=O have been obtained¹⁰ as evident from the spectrum of **14** (δ 189.7 and 182.4). CMR does not make clear-cut distinction between one chelated C=O and both chelated C=O.

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In view of the situation explained above, it is concluded that IR helps in distinguishing between 1,5- and 1,8-dioxygenation patterns in anthraquinones provided that there is no hydroxylation at C-4.

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